

Velocity of Reaction in Mixed Solvents. Part II. The Velocity of Reaction between Sodium Thiosulphate and Alkyl Iodides in Organic Solvents—Water Mixtures.

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It has been shown in Part I (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 59) that the velocity of reaction between potassium persulphate and potassium iodide in water is lowered by the addition of alcohol, glycerol, glycol and pyridine, and that no simple relation exists between velocity constants and the viscosities and the dielectric constants of the mixtures.

In the present investigation the reaction between alkyl iodides and sodium thiosulphate has been studied in mixtures of organic solvents and water. The kinetics of the reactions between sodium thiosulphate and alkyl iodides in aqueous solutions have been studied by Slator (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, 85, 1285). It was found that the order of the reaction is second as expected from the equation of the reaction,

EXPERIMENTAL.

The velocity of reaction between methyl and ethyl iodides with sodium thiosulphate has been studied in mixtures of water with methyl, ethyl, *n*- and *iso*-propyl alcohols, glycerol and glycol.

Methyl and ethyl iodides were prepared and purified in the laboratory and their purity was tested by determining their boiling points. Sodium thiosulphate used was Merck's "extra pure" chemical. All the organic solvents used were Merck's "extra pure" chemicals. Alcohols were further purified by distillation over calcium chloride.

Solutions of sodium thiosulphate and alkyl iodides were prepared in water, redistilled from alkaline potassium permanganate, fresh every time an experiment was performed. A known amount of the organic solvent was added to one of the solutions and the two solutions were kept separately in a thermostat maintained at 25° and were mixed together when they had acquired the temperature of the bath.

5 C.c. of the reaction mixture were taken out in ice-cold water at definite intervals of time and the amount of sodium thiosulphate

present in the solution was immediately determined by titration against standard iodine.

The velocity constant, K , of the reactions was then calculated from the bimolecular formula,

$$k = \frac{1}{t(a-b)} \log \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)}$$

where a = initial concentration of sodium thiosulphate in terms of c.c. of iodine solution.

b = initial concentration of methyl iodide in terms of c.c. of iodine solution.

x = the amount of the iodine used up in terms of iodine solution in time t .

$$a = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{b(a-x)}{a(b-x)} = k(a-b).$$

The results obtained with methyl and ethyl iodides are given below.

Methyl Iodide and Sodium Thiosulphate.

In order to avoid the loss of methyl iodide due to evaporation in aqueous and aqueous alcohol solutions with low contents of alcohols, the reactions were carried out in a special type of vessel, shown in Fig. 1. With higher contents of alcohols ordinary conical flasks with rubber stoppers were used, for in these solutions there is no loss of methyl iodide due to evaporation.

FIG. 1.

The wide glass tube *A* contained the solutions used in the experiments and was connected with a 5 c.c. pipette in such a manner that exactly 5 c.c. of the reaction mixture could be easily taken out. Evaporation from the surface was prevented by means of the float *B*.

The concentrations of sodium thiosulphate and methyl iodide used in the experiments were 0.03454*N* and 0.03408*N* respectively. The values of *a*, *b* and *x* are expressed in terms of c.c. of 0.009247 *N* solution of iodine required for 5 c.c. of the reaction mixtures.

TABLE I.

Solvent - Water.

<i>t.</i>	<i>a-x.</i>	<i>s</i>	<i>b-x.</i>	<i>c</i> × 10 ⁴ .
4	16.25	2.43	15.98	20.0
10	14.1	4.58	13.83	19.0
20	11.78	6.99	11.48	19.0
31	9.58	9.70	9.31	19.6
40	8.21	10.47	7.94	20.1
Mean value of <i>c</i> × 10 ⁴ = 19.5.			Mean value of <i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ = 7.22	
			Duplicate .. = 7.28	
			Mean = 7.25	

TABLE II.

Mean Values of k × 10⁴.

Organic solvent.	Percentage of the organic solvent.						
	0	10	20	30	40	50	60
Methyl alcohol ...	7.25	16.3	19.1	—	30.2	37.9	43.0
Ethyl alcohol ...	7.25	15.8	22.8	32.5	38.9	36.5	36.4
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol ...	7.25	18.7	23.5	18.9	14.7	—	11.7
<i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol ...	7.25	17.1	25.9	29.2	25.2	22.0	19.2
Glycol ...	7.25	8.18	—	—	—	—	—
Glycerol ...	7.25	5.66	—	—	—	—	—

The velocity constants have been plotted against the composition of the mixtures and the curves obtained are shown in Fig 2.

*Velocity Constant—Composition Curves
(Methyl iodide—Sodium thiosulphate).*

FIG. 2.

Ethyl Iodide and Sodium Thiosulphate.

Ethyl iodide is not so volatile as methyl iodide and hence reactions were carried out in conical flasks.

Concentrations of ethyl iodide and sodium thiosulphate used were 0.02582N and 0.03455N respectively. The values of a , b and x are expressed in terms of c.c. of 0.007463N solution of iodine required for 5 c.c. of the reaction mixture.

TABLE III.
Solvent—Water.

	<i>a</i> — <i>x</i> .	<i>x</i> .	<i>b</i> — <i>x</i> .	<i>c</i> × 10 ⁵ .
20	20.18	0.60	14.75	22.5
40	19.75	1.03	11.32	20.0
60	19.32	1.46	13.89	20.0
80	18.84	1.94	18.41	20.0
100	18.41	2.37	12.98	20.0
125	17.91	2.87	12.48	20.2
145	17.49	3.29	12.06	20.5

Mean value of *c* × 10⁵ = 20.5 Mean value of *k* × 10⁴ = 3.8.

TABLE IV.
Mean Values of *k* × 10⁴.

Organic solvent.	Percentage of the organic solvent.							
	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	
Methyl alcohol	...	3.8	—	6.77	—	8.74	—	10.8
Ethyl alcohol	...	3.8	7.42	10.0	12.30	12.30	10.40	—
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	...	3.8	7.56	9.16	5.56	3.51	2.44	—
<i>iso</i> Propyl alcohol	...	3.8	8.47	11.5	9.66	6.22	4.64	—

The velocity constants have been plotted against the composition of the mixtures and the curves obtained are shown in Fig. 3.

Velocity Constant Composition Curves
(Ethyl iodide and Sodium thiosulphate).

FIG. 3.

Discussion of Results.

Results described in the Tables II and IV show that the velocity constant varies as the composition of the medium in which the reaction is taking place is varied. Higher concentrations of the solvent than 60 per cent. could not be used due to the insolubility of sodium thiosulphate in mixtures containing more than 60 per cent. of the organic solvent.

But it will be seen from Figs. 2 and 3 that as the concentration of alcohols in the mixtures is increased, the value of the velocity constants at first increases and then begins to decrease (cf. maximum points A and B in the curves 2 and 3). Methyl alcohol is an exception to the above generalisation; no maximum point is observed in this case but the velocity constant continually increases with the increase in the concentration of methyl alcohol in the mixture. It is possible that the maximum point may also be obtained in this case at higher concentrations of the mixtures.

The maximum values of the velocity constants of the two reactions in various alcoholic mixtures decrease as

The increase in the number of OH-groups in the molecule of the solvent also decreases the accelerating effect. The mean values of the velocity constants in reaction mixtures containing 10 per cent. of methyl alcohol, glycol and glycerol are—

Solvent.	Methyl alcohol.	Glycol.	Glycerol.
$k \times 10^4$	16.8	8.1	5.68

Dielectric constant of the medium does not seem to influence the rate of reaction to a great extent. Whereas the dielectric constants of alcohol—water mixtures continually decrease with the increase in the concentration of the alcohol, the velocity constants in these reactions have been found first to increase, reach a maximum and then to decrease.

But it is possible that the rate of reaction may not depend on the dielectric constant of the medium but on the dielectric constant of the reaction mixture. Ionisation of electrolytes, *i.e.*, the electrical resistance of a system depends to a great extent on the dielectric constant of the system; hence the electrical resistances of mixtures of methyl iodide and sodium thiosulphate in aqueous ethyl alcohol mixtures were determined.

The reaction mixtures were prepared in the same manner as in the experiments described above. The resistance was measured by,

Kohlrusch's bridge method at 25°. It was found that as the reaction proceeded, the resistance of the system gradually increased but the total increase was not more than 3-4 ohms. The resistances of the reaction mixtures in various ethyl alcohol-water mixtures at the start of the reaction are as follows:—

Percentage composition	10	20	30	40	50
Resistance in ohms	90.4	118.1	176.0	219.7	259.0

These values were plotted against composition and a straight line curve was obtained as shown in Fig. 4. This indicates that the

*Resistance—Composition Curves of the System
Na₂S₂O₈ + MeI in water-ethyl alcohol mixtures.*

FIG. 4.

resistance of the reaction mixture increases regularly with the increase in the concentration of the alcohol in the mixtures. These results show that the causes responsible for the maximum points in the velocity constant—composition curves in no way influence the total resistance of the system.

It will be seen from the following table that the maximum points occur at the composition of the alcohol-water mixtures corresponding

to the composition of the known hydrates of alcohol in aqueous solution in the mobile state (*cf.* Salazar, *Anal. Fis. Quim.*, 1921, 22, 275).

TABLE V.

$\text{CH}_3\text{I} + \text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$.			$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{I} + \text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$.		
Hydrate.	Theoretical composition.	Composition of maximum points.	Hydrates.	Theoretical composition.	Composition of maximum points.
EtOH, 6H ₂ O	36.24 %	36 %	EtOH, 6H ₂ O	36.24 %	35.2 %
PrOH, 16H ₂ O	20.17 %	18 %	PrOH, 16H ₂ O	20.17 %	18 %

It appears, therefore, probable that the influence of the molecular compound formation of the organic solvent is more important than the effect of the dielectric constant or viscosity.

The formation of these molecular compounds has got, probably, a two-fold effect on the rate of reaction.

1. It decreases the active mass of the free solvent. This will have an accelerating effect on the rate of reaction due to the increase in the concentration of the reactants.

2. Hydrated molecules, being more complex than the molecules of single solvents, offer greater resistance to the reacting molecules or ions. This will have a retarding effect on the rate of reaction.

The observed effect will, therefore, be determined by these two factors.

Jones and his co-workers have shown that ions get hydrated in aqueous solution and molecules are either not hydrated or hydrated to a small extent. Goldschmidt (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1907, 60, 728) has assumed that ions also combine with alcohols and form ion-alcoholates. These effects will decrease the mobility of the ions and may further retard the rate of reaction.

Summary.

1. Reactions between sodium thiosulphate and methyl and ethyl iodides have been studied in various organic solvents and water mixtures.

2. Organic solvents have been found to exert a definite influence, acceleration or retardation.

3. There is no direct relationship between the velocity constants of the reactions in these mixtures and their composition.

4. In a homologous series of solvents the addition of the CH_2 -group in the molecule of the solvent regularly accelerates or retards the rate of reaction.

5. Increase of OH-groups in the molecule of the solvents decreases the velocity constant.

6. Viscosity and dielectric constant of the mixture do not produce any appreciable effect.

7. Maximum points in the velocity constant and composition curves correspond to molecular compounds of the organic solvents with water.

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